

Design, Testing and Long-Term Experience with Sandwich Materials on Plastics Basis in the Building Sector

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ABSTRACT

In the building sector multi-layer composite materials, so-called sandwich structures, are being used to an increasing extent even for load-bearing purposes because, inter alia, they combine small deformations and a high carrying capacity under flexural loads with a low structural weight.

The particular mechanical behaviour of these structures is a combination of the properties of the single layers and can to a high degree be calculated by means of available theoretical methods, for short-term as well as for long-term loadings. Different failure modes, that may occur with respect to the internal stress distribution on hand, have to be taken into consideration during all steps in design and testing work.

As sandwich compounds are not-yet-proven building materials they often have to go through difficult and time-consuming approval procedures, until an increasing experience will offer a better basis for acceptance and confidence. It is therefore necessary to initiate a nonrestricted exchange of information concerning long-term experience and case histories of structural sandwich applications in order to let these extraordinary materials play their part in satisfying the building requirements of the present-day situation, including architectural as well as energy saving aspects.

INTRODUCTION

Sandwich materials are composed of two covering layers, consisting of materials such as metal, plastics, wood, asbestos cement, and an intermediate core, for instance of metal, plastic or cardboard honeycomb structures, balsawood or rigid plastic foams. Their load-bearing properties are based on the capacity to withstand normal stress of the two relatively strong covering layers which are supported and held over a large distance in relation to their thickness by the extremely light and relatively soft core, whereby a high moment of inertia is obtained on subjection to bending stress. The core itself is only subjected to a minor degree of stress, for the most part shear stress.

For most applications sandwich structures are calculated to withstand a required level of static or dynamic short-term loads and have to suffer long-term loads of a small amount only. In the building sector, however, they often have to be dimensioned as load-bearing structures subjected to static long-term loads, too.

For ideal, i.e. flawless composite units, existing methods of calculation permit, with adequate accuracy a theoretical estimation of the load-bearing and deformation behaviour. In practice, however, in normal use or under laboratory conditions failure frequently occurs well before the calculated limit of load-bearing capacity is reached, because of variations from the idealized assumptions made for the purposes of calculation.

The mechanisms which occur to sandwich panels during subsection to certain kinds of stress are shown schematically in Fig. 1, and include compound imperfections, here core-to-facesheet disbondings.

BEHAVIOUR UNDER SHORT-TERM LOADING

Fundamental theoretical data on the particular mechanical properties of multi-layer composite materials are already available and form the basis of all design and testing work. The types of failure occurring with sandwich structures composed of varying individual layers and the exact and simplified methods of calculation to be applied are listed together with rough error estimations in (1).

Here the intention is to explain the types of failure in the light of the main stresses vertically to the plane of the panel (bending) and in the plane of the panel (stability).

When a sandwich structure with soft core material is subjected to flexural load the shear deformations must not be neglected, if significant transverse forces (and resulting shear stresses) are on hand, which are, for the most part, absorbed by the core. Only in the case of large spans do the pure bending deformations (due to normal stresses) predominate. The exact as well as the simplified stress distributions are illustrated in Fig. 2, together with various sandwich layer compositions and including different types of reinforcement.

In the event of stresses affecting the stability, the Euler equation only applies approximately for very great buckling lengths. During buckling, a shear deformation occurs in addition to the bending deformation as a result of the induced transverse force. This yields a critical buckling load with components from the covering layers and the core material.

In the case of sandwich panels with light core (low modulus), covering layers subjected to compression can, above a critical stress level - the so-called "crumpling stress" - form sinusoidal corrugations. When this happens, the covering layer loses its load-bearing capacity to a large extent and finally detaches itself from the core. This "crumpling stress" is primarily dependent on the rigidity of covering layer and core material. It presupposes, however, a bonding between the layers which extends over the full surface area, which is not always the case in practice.

With light-core composite units, additional local stresses must also be particularly taken into account. Especially in the case of thin covering layers a soft core material is compressed under punctual or linear loads perpendicular to the surface as a result of its low rigidity. Local deformations of the core and the layer can impair the overall load-bearing capacity of the composite material and thus lead to premature failure.

With sandwich elements, the varying possible kinds of failure are always to be taken into consideration even in the normal case, according to thickness and properties of the individual layers. Transitional areas from one failure mode to another can be determined by mathematical simulation on the basis of the simplified calculation according to Fig. 2, right section. Calculations and comparative experiments were carried out on sandwich beams of varying length for subsection to flexural and buckling stress (1).

For the symmetrically constructed three-layer composite structures both rigid Polyurethane foam (bulk density 50 to 250 kg/m³) as well as rigid Polyvinylchloride foam modified with Isocyanate (bulk density 30 to 80 kg/m³) were taken as core materials in thicknesses of 20 to 100 mm, and for the covering layers thermosetting polyester resin reinforced with glassfibres (mats and fabrics) was used in thicknesses of 1 to 4 mm.

In Fig. 3 the various failure criteria (as maximum tolerable line loads) for a bending beam under uniform line load have been plotted as a function of span. It can be seen that with long spans there occurs a failure of the covering layers as a result of exceeding their tensile or compressive strength.

Below a so-called "critical transition length" the failure is, on the other hand, attributable to reaching the shear strength of the core. With very short spans the tolerable line load is naturally limited by the compressive strength of the core. "Crumpling" of the covering layers does not occur with the parameter combination selected here.

In Fig. 4 the different failure criteria (as maximum tolerable compressive loads) for an upright section with an articulated mounting under subjection to compression have been plotted as a function of buckling length.

It can be seen that with medium buckling lengths the buckling load calculated in the simplified manner hardly differs from the exact solution and both approximate the Euler-load (for shear-resistant cores) at great buckling lengths. Below a so-called "critical buckling length" the failure is on the other hand attributable to reaching the crumpling stress of the covering layers without overall buckling of the upright section. The tolerable compressive load then remains constant until the buckling length becomes less than the crumpling length of the covering layers. Then the load increases again until the compressive strength of the covering layers is reached.

The considerations set out here apply to panels with homogenous cores and open cut edges, so that an unhindered shifting of the covering layers against each other can take place. The shear deformation can be considerably diminished and the shear strength increased if individual stiff anti-shear strips are incorporated in the core and/or special connections between the covering layers are fitted to the side edges of the panels so as to withstand shear forces, see also Fig. 2. In many cases it can also be advantageous to design the overall sandwich with covering layers of different thicknesses, e.g. when punctual or linear loads are locally introduced on one side only.

In many applications, particularly in the building industry, a temperature difference between the covering layers must be taken into account as an additional loading factor. This may lead to considerable additional deformations or stresses according to the manner in which the panels are fixed.

BEHAVIOUR UNDER LONG-TERM LOADING

In the last few years fundamental theoretical and experimental investigations have been conducted into different plastic as well as sandwich materials under statical loading, taking into account the specific long-term deformation behaviour of organic materials by using different formulations.

On the one hand they covered single-layer, solid plastics with various reinforcement materials, as well as, on the other hand, profiled sandwich units with steel covering layers and plastic foam core (2). The deformation behaviour of the rigid foams normally used for sandwich units has also already been largely investigated (3).

Hitherto, however, only isolated investigations have been made into the load-bearing and deformation behaviour of multi-layer materials, where all layers consist of plastics and tend to "creep" under long-term statical loading (4). Fundamental interrelations between the deformation behaviour of the individual layers themselves and the multi-layer sandwich material composed thereof have now been determined. The investigation covered sandwich units in varying combinations of individual layers which creep a lot, only a little or not at all, in order to include the whole spectrum of possible multi-layer combinations. The results of this work will be introduced here by reference to certain basic perceptions.

It is assumed to be known that all organic materials manifest a greater or lesser increase in the initial deformation under long-term permanent loading as a result of "creep". This depends on the structure of the material, the degree of load and the temperature plus other environmental conditions. If the overall deformation is minor, it is largely reversible, but above material-specific deformation limits irreversible damage occurs, and finally failure.

The increase in deformation over time is usually determined in tests under practice-simulated loading and plotted in "creep curves" over the loading duration, Fig. 5.

As creep tests are costly and time-consuming, an extrapolation to the estimated or required life of a structure is desired and in the meantime officially recognized as the basis of dimensioning in the building industry. In doing this it must be taken into account that certain plot modes can, according to the type of material and speed of creep, lead to incorrect results in the extrapolation, see also Fig. 5. Good precision in the extrapolation over a maximum of ten times the test period has been obtained in the application of known rheological models and empirical creep equations, Fig. 6.

With extrapolation attempts over more than one decade, a larger uncertainty factor is to be taken into account.

The mathematical estimation of the creep behaviour of flat sandwich beams follows from the mathematical addition of the deformation portions, determined over the long-term or extrapolated, for shear in the core and tension/compression in the covering layers. In this the already-mentioned simplified equations of the bending mechanics are applied, but instead of the usual elasticity and shear moduli the relevant creep moduli are employed for the period of time to be examined under constant long-term loading.

By way of the example of thin beams under four-point flexural load, a good agreement between this calculation and corresponding creep tests on the sandwich structures themselves has been proved, Fig. 7.

The creep behaviour of very different individual materials have corresponding effects on the creep deformation of the sandwich structure - according to the degree of load on the individual layers.

In a flat sandwich element with rigid foam core and without anti-shear strips or edge connections between the covering layers the long-term increase in deformation may be strongly influenced by the creep of the relatively soft (in terms of shear) core material in contrast to the stiffer and more creep-resistant covering layers.

It has been found out, however, that sandwich structures with steel covering layers yield significantly smaller creep factors than the beams with PVC covering layers, irrespective of the nature of the core material. This results from the relatively low degree of shear compared to the total deformation due to the sandwich geometry and load arrangement selected here, see also Fig.7.

Accordingly, the designer should design a sandwich structure on the basis of a suitable choice of materials and cross section geometry in order to keep the increase in deformation under permanent load small.

If, however, these means are inadequate to keep the long-term deformation within permissible limits then it may be necessary to apply additional anti-shear strips or edge connections made of more creep-resistant materials. In the extreme case the covering layers or the complete sandwich are to be profiled in a suitable manner.

The estimation of the strength of sandwich components subjected to long-term loads, however, poses greater difficulties than the assessment of the creep behaviour because strength values from sandwich specimens manifest a great scatter.

Flaws, e.g. in the bond, impair the deformation behaviour only to a minor extent; on the other hand, with regard to the load-bearing capacity, they can lead to early and possibly catastrophic failure.

Even if the individual components only manifest a minor deterioration of the mechanical properties over time, this great susceptibility to flaws in the area of the necessary bond between covering layer and core remains, which renders it difficult to determine the overall deterioration with any certainty. That is the reason, why possible imperfections with sandwich materials have to be taken into account by additional long-term safety factors or by corresponding tests, as shall be discussed lateron.

TESTING

On the basis of available theoretical knowledge and long-term practical experience with sandwich elements, preliminary guidelines have been worked out by the competent bodies of the Federal German Building Sector, which, alongside the dimensioning, embrace in particular also recommendations for the material and structural component tests necessary for a proof of suitability.

Accordingly, tensile, compression and shear tests on the covering layer and core materials are to be conducted for the determination of short-term and long-term moduli as well as strength values, also at the maximum surface temperatures to be expected.

The bonding effect between the individual layers is determined in the tensile test, the adhesion having to be greater than the core strength.

The temperature resistance of the sandwich structure can be additionally proved by subsection of the covering layers to heat up to the expected surface temperature and over longer test periods.

This procedure is already widely used in testing practice and also for quality control purposes and makes it possible to detect with certainty unpermissible bonding flaws from a certain surface area. Smaller detachments or adhesion flaws between covering layer and core can be determined with the aid of a relatively new optical measuring procedure, which can indicate local bulging of a few micrometers in height on extensive surface areas. It is this the holographic interferometry, which, by means of laser illumination, makes visible minor local differences in deformation on the surface of an object under suitable loading.

A detailed report on this subject has already been made (5). The procedure is still extremely expensive in terms of equipment and personnel so that it is still not very widespread in quality control, but increasingly so in the development of new processing techniques for sandwich materials.

Within the framework of the proof of suitability, for the determination of load bearing and deformation behaviour of the sandwich structure, further building component tests are to be carried out under practice-simulated loading and temperature conditions, also over longer test periods.

If only minor or no shear stresses are present (e.g. in the case of membrane or shell support structures) a long-term test on the core material and creep tests on the finished component can be dispensed with.

Beyond the proof of load bearing capacity, further proofs are to be provided from case to case covering usability in its widest sense and also, e.g. construction physics (water vapour permeation, thermal and sound insulation) and fire behaviour.

EXAMPLES OF APPLICATIONS AND LONG-TERM EXPERIENCE

In the German building sector, as in other fields of technology, the extent to which multi-layer sandwich materials are used is still far behind that of other countries, e.g. the USA and Great Britain, and possibly Japan. This is partly because of the necessary approval procedure which have to be gone through with the authorities in Germany prior to the introduction of not-yet-proven building materials and methods. Particularly strict are the fire regulations.

Nevertheless a number of building project have already been approved and completed, which are listed in (6) but cannot be dealt with individually here.

The projects involve complete single-storey houses or only roof units, but predominantly wall or facade components, Fig. 8. The latter, in particular, have been used in great numbers over the last 15 years or so, for special structures in the telecommunications field and are hence not subject to general building law but fall under the authority of the competent civil and military bodies. For such special building projects the approval procedure can often be simplified, as long as there are no recognized architectural rules in existence.

The facade units discussed here are used for the claddings of the platform superstructures of towers (concrete or steel framework structures), and in addition to thermal insulation properties often have to satisfy requirements with regard to electromagnetic aspects.

The sandwich units consist of PUR rigid foam cores with covering layers of glassfibre reinforced plastics and/or sheet steel. They have bridge spans of up to 3 m with panel lengths of up to 7 m. Individual panel segments are either joined together in a fully force-transmitting manner by splice-pieces or joined to the bearing profile sections of the substructure in an articulated manner by screws. The panels have no special edge reinforcements, so that any shear forces must be fully borne by the core.

The dimensioning of the sandwich panels is carried out in these cases according to the methods of calculation already introduced. They have to be regarded as articulated and slide-mounted flexural support members under predominantly short-term loading, dictated by the maximum wind pressure, and subjection to additional long-term loading attributable to temperature changes.

The positive experience of the past 10 years has proved that the sandwich mode of construction selected here has fully lived up to expectations in terms of choice of material, dimensioning and design. Damage which has occurred during the development phase has, furthermore, confirmed the necessity of using qualitatively high-grade, temperature-resistant materials and appropriate manufacturing processes, e.g. in the bonding of the individual layers to each other.

Not least important is the necessity of selecting an optimal combination of individual layers, taking into account the principles of construction physics, as a prerequisite for permanent functional capacity under changing climatic ambient conditions. Similarly important is the suitable execution of the seals at penetration points, connection joints and points of introduction of forces - all of which are generally problematic in the construction field.

To summarize it can be stated that it is sensible, in the light of the difficult present-day energy situation, not only to provide buildings with a thermal insulation which satisfies higher requirements than have hitherto been set, but also, in certain cases, to execute the facade as a thermally insulated load-bearing sandwich structure. In the past a hindrance to this has often been an inadequate fire behaviour. However it is nowadays possible to obtain a fire category "B 1 - low flammability" by selecting suitable materials for the sandwich unit, even if no non-combustible metal covering layers are used. Hence the excellent thermal insulation properties of PUR rigid foam materials can be fully utilized for energy savings in the heating of buildings.

It should always be kept in mind that with a thermal insulation layer increased by 5 cm above the minimum requirements a saving of up to 200 litres of heating oil per m² of outer wall can be made over a period of 10 years for a negligible outlay of a few (1 to 5) kilograms of organic raw material.

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Fig. 1

Sandwich structures subjected to different kinds of service stress (schematic illustration)

Fig. 2

left: various sandwich layer compositions and types of reinforcement

right: stress distributions (exact and simplified) for a plane sandwich subjected to flexural load

1. rigid core and layers
2. soft core, rigid layers
3. soft core, thin layers

Fig. 3

Maximum line load vs. span and occurring failure modes for sandwich beams with different core materials

Fig. 4

Maximum compressive load vs. buckling length and occurring failure modes for upright sandwich sections with different core materials

Fig. 5

Experimental values of shear deformation vs. loading duration ("creep" curves) for a rigid plastic foam.

Different plot modes and resulting extrapolation uncertainties

Fig. 6

Experimental and calculated "creep" curves (according to Fig. 5).

Application of different available formulations and measuring periods

Fig. 7

Experimental and calculated deflections due to "creep" for a sandwich beam with foamed plastic core

Top: comparison between "creep" deflections for different loading periods

Bottom: comparison between theory and experiment for a loading period of 1000 hours

$G(t), E(t)$ = creep moduli for shear and normal stresses according to the loading duration on hand

Fig. 8 Sandwich structures as claddings for superstructures of telecommunication towers

